

The AURORAE (Air qUality foRecast fOR Arctic communitiEs) service

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Abstract

Air pollution represents the first environmental health problem in EU. The EU Action Plan: "Towards a Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil" provides a vision for 2025, including 2030 targets such as improving air quality to reduce the number of premature deaths. In this technical report we present AURORAE (Air qUality foRecast fOR Arctic communitiEs), an online dashboard providing accessible air pollution PM₁₀ forecasts tailored for European Arctic communities of countries in the north Europe (Norway, Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Iceland) using a novel approach that involves the use of Artificial Intelligence algorithms. Our methodology consists in providing a 2-days air quality forecast tailored for about 100 monitoring stations distributed in North Europe and European Arctic. The forecast at the selected monitoring stations is released daily on the AURORAE website (<https://aurorae.azurewebsites.net/>) along with near-real time concentrations. This online forecast service may empower local communities and support decisions regarding pollution reduction and prevention. It might further improve the use of local air pollution observations by providing locally more accurate forecasts and bringing feedback information to models on their agreement with observations.

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1 Introduction

The Arctic is warming two to three times more than other regions (Masson-Delmotte et al., 2018). A coherent system of Earth Observation is needed to observe the current changes, predict future climate variations, and improve mitigation measures. In the Arctic the observational systems for the environment are often fragmented and inadequate to fulfil the needs of people living and working in the area. Arctic PASSION (<https://arcticpassion.eu/>) is a Horizon 2020 project and an innovative pan-Arctic Observation and Monitoring action that aims at facing the challenges that people living and working in the Arctic are experiencing. In particular, the project endeavours integrating and improving existing Arctic observing system elements with new services and improving data interoperability. The JRC is participating in this project in the Work Package 4 'Implementing EuroGEO services to provide new information to support emergency preparedness, food security, responses to climate and socio-economic changes' through the development of one of the eight 'Pilot Services' called 'Local Atmospheric Pollutant Forecast'-Service' (PS5).

For a long time, the atmosphere in the Arctic has been considered free from pollution until explorers in the '50s observed the phenomenon of Arctic Haze, which consists in the accumulation of pollutants in the lowest part of the troposphere during winter and early spring (Mitchell, 1957). This phenomenon is driven by low temperatures during the cold Arctic winter, trapping the atmospheric pollutants close to the Earth surface (Schmale et al., 2018). Particulate matter (PM) is an atmospheric pollutant which could be found in the Arctic and consists of a mixture of solids and liquid droplets containing several chemical species such as nitrate, sulphate, organic compounds, and many others. Nowadays residential combustion for heating, shipping, oil extraction and metal smelting represent the main local PM sources in the extreme North. Due to the small size of the particulate, with 10 μm of equivalent diameter or less, called PM_{10} , the particles can enter in the lungs while breathing, and exposure to high concentrations might cause respiratory problems, cardiovascular diseases and cancer (Megido et al., 2017; Seaton et al., 1995). PM_{10} concentration limits established by the World Health Organization for PM_{10} are 15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ mean annual concentration and 45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ daily mean concentration (WHO, 2021), while the new European Union Directive on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe indicates 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as the limit for mean annual concentration and 45 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ as daily mean concentration for a maximum of 18 days per year (Parliament, 2024). Moreover, the EU Action Plan "Towards a Zero Pollution for Air, Water and Soil" provides a vision for 2025, including 2030 targets such as improving air quality to reduce the number of premature deaths. Considering the adverse health effects caused by PM_{10} , an accurate forecast of its concentrations is essential for pollution mitigation and emergency preparedness in Arctic villages and cities.

The forecast of PM_{10} concentrations over Europe, including the Arctic, is performed by the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS), based on an ensemble of 11 state-of-the-art numerical air quality models (Marécal et al., 2015). CAMS predictions, nonetheless, have uncertainties that mainly related to errors in the input data such as initial state estimation, model parametrization, emissions, and model algorithms (Bertrand et al., 2022). CAMS forecasted concentrations appear to agree less with in-situ measurements of PM_{10} in Northern Europe in comparison to other regions (Schulz et al., 2020). Recently several studies implemented artificial intelligence techniques to improve forecasting accuracy for air quality index or pollutant concentration (Méndez et al., 2023) also specifically for the Arctic (Fazzini et al., 2023). We address the disagreement between CAMS forecasts and observations with the development of a PM_{10} Transformer based Deep Learning forecast model. It combines in-situ measurements from about 100 monitoring stations, nine 48 hours CAMS PM_{10} forecasts, and a 48 hours forecast of six

meteorological variables produced by Integrated Forecast System (IFS) of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) for countries in the European Arctic (Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Finland and Iceland). Our novel approach delivers locally more accurate PM₁₀ forecast tailored for northern communities. The PM₁₀ forecasts produced by the Neural Network (NN) model are published with daily frequency for about 100 monitoring stations on the AURORAE dashboard, an easy-to-use interactive map where also near-real time concentrations are displayed. The forecasts can be easily downloaded along with PM₁₀ near-real data for each station.

In this technical report, we describe all the phases of the development of the 'Local Atmospheric Pollutant Forecast' Service: from scoping, the development of the Deep Learning (DL) approach, the dashboard structure and the validation of the forecast results. In addition, the two final chapters focus on data curation and the interaction with the stakeholders that helped to shape the final version of the online platform.

2 Objective and scope

In the Arctic, global warming is creating advantageous conditions for new economic activities such as shipping and oil and gas extraction, extending local sources of atmospheric pollution (Arnold et al., 2016). In addition, biomass burning from domestic heating and boreal wildfires represent relevant sources of PM₁₀ affecting northern communities (Schmale et al., 2018). Considering the impact of atmospheric pollutants on public health, releasing reliable short-term forecasts is essential to support national governments and organizational stakeholders (Arctic Council, Arctic Science Ministerial, etc.) in aligning to the European Air Quality Directive 2008/50/EC, to plan policies and to limit the exposure of the population (Bertrand et al., 2022). The production of an accurate and accessible PM₁₀ forecast in Northern European countries is therefore critical, especially to empower Arctic communities and support decisions on pollution reduction and prevention.

The objective of the ‘Local Atmospheric Pollutant Forecast’ Service is to improve the available PM₁₀ CAMS forecasts and customize the prediction for municipalities in North Europe and the European Arctic. The Service also provides an easy-to use web interface that allows access to near-real time PM₁₀ concentrations data and forecast for about a hundred air pollution monitoring stations. The dashboard is designed for a non-scientific audience and provides an interactive map where communities’ representatives, policymakers and citizens can easily visualize and download PM₁₀ at the selected stations. The service, in addition, aims at providing added value to air pollution observations, improving data accessibility and interoperability. Our approach may strengthen the effectiveness of the air pollution monitoring stations network and provide additional societal benefits to people living in the Arctic.

Figure 1. Schematic on the relationships among data from emissions and observations of atmospheric pollutants, model simulations to estimate the impact on air quality and climate and how this information is essential to manage emissions and define regulations

Source: AMAP, 2021

3 Air pollution forecast models

The two main methodologies used to predict PM₁₀ concentrations are numerical (deterministic) and statistical models. Numerical models, also known as Chemical Transport Models (CTMs), predict air pollutant concentrations, simulating considering the physical transformations and chemical reactions of the pollutants. Those models involve solving a set of differential equations describing chemical and physical processes happening in the atmosphere, which require a detailed knowledge of initial state conditions and external forcing such as pollutant sources, temporal variation of the emission quantity, chemical composition of emissions and, inflow of pollutants from remote regions and chemical and physical processes happening in the atmosphere (Hrust et al., 2009). However, due to the lack of extensive observations describing initial conditions in-situ measurements, data about accurate information on emissions rate and meteorological parameters, forecast by these models' predictions are often associated with uncertainties depending on the level of simplification (Qiu et al., 2023). Deterministic models often accurately estimate PM₁₀ frequent events, but they seem to less accurately detect extreme peaks in pollution (Shahraiyani & Sodoudi, 2016), making them unsuitable for mitigation planning (Alam & McNabola, 2015). In the past 20 years, several CTMs have been developed to provide gas-phase species and PM forecast and such as EMEP (Simpson et al., 2012), TM5 (Krol et al., 2005) and REMOTE (Langmann et al., 2008), while others such as CHIMERE (Menut et al., 2021) and LOTOS-EUROS (Schaap et al., 2008) are used by CAMS to perform the ensemble forecast (Marécal et al., 2015).

Statistical models, on the other hand, have been successfully developed for the spatio-temporal prediction of air pollutants locally and at small spatial scales. Based on assumptions on statistical properties of model variables, they may implicitly detect the complex site-specific relationship between observed pollutant concentration and some explanatory variables avoiding the exact specification of emissions, meteorological conditions and external influences (Alam & McNabola, 2015; Shahraiyani & Sodoudi, 2016). Explanatory variables may include arbitrary selected meteorological parameters which represent one of the main controls of PM₁₀ concentrations. The transport and dispersion processes of pollutants are mainly governed by wind speed and direction, while solar radiation and air temperature are involved in the formation of secondary fraction (Grivas & Chaloulakou, 2006). In the Arctic, in particular, the planetary boundary layer height represents a relevant parameter, low temperatures and subsidence in high-pressure systems often cause inversions that suppress vertical mixing of the air and promote pollutant accumulation close to the ground (Mölders & Kramm, 2018). Moreover, information on sources such as vehicular/shipping traffic regime, land use patterns, oil/gas extraction activities and population density influence the spatial and temporal variations of PM₁₀ as well (Law et al., 2017). The main drawback of statistical models is that they do not explicitly consider physical and chemical processes, consequently they could be applied for forecasting only to the area for which they are built for (Shahraiyani & Sodoudi, 2016).

3.1 CAMS models

The regional air quality forecast for Europe is released daily by CAMS, an ensemble of 11 state-of-the-art numerical atmospheric composition models developed by different institutions (Table 1). They are CTMs that simulate atmospheric chemistry and rely on the weather forecast, chemical conditions and wildfire emissions released by the Centre for ECMWF (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts>), which affect the transport, mixing and removal of pollutants (Horálek et al., 2020) (Figure 2). They are characterized by different horizontal and vertical

resolutions (Table 1) and use different initial conditions (Collin, 2020). Each model performs daily analyses of pollutants near the surface by assimilating 1-day old observations. Observations (satellite and surface) are split into two sets used in the data assimilation process and for statistical assessments of forecasts and analyses. The forecasts and analyses from all 11 models are combined in calculating the median value of the model outputs, which provides the best 11 model ensemble estimate named ENSEMBLE. It provides a 4-day forecast at hourly resolution of the main atmospheric pollutants concentrations, including PM₁₀, in the lowest layers of the atmosphere (east boundary=25.0° W, west=45.0° E, south=30.0° N, north=72.0°) with a horizontal coverage of 0.1°x0.1° (approximately 10 to 20 km) and a vertical coverage of 5000 m (Collin, 2020).

Table 1. Main characteristics of the air quality regional models used by CAMS (Collin, 2020; Marécal et al., 2015).

Model Institution	Institution	Horizontal Resolution	Vertical Resolution	Assimilated Measurements
CHIMERE	INERIS1	0.1° x 0.1°	8 levels, top at 500 hPa	O ₃ and PM ₁₀ from surface stations
EMEP	MET Norway2	0.25° x 0.125°	20 levels, top at 100hPa	top at 100 hPa NO ₂ columns from OMI/Aura remote
EURAD-IM	RIU UK3	15 km, Lambert projection	23 levels, top at 100 hPa	O ₃ , NO, NO ₂ , SO ₂ , CO, PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} from surface stations, NO ₂ from remote sensing column retrievals, CO profiles
LOTOS-EUROS	KNMI4	0.25° x 0.125 °	34 levels, top at 3.5 km	km O ₃ from surface stations
MATCH	SMHI5	0.2° x 0.2°	52 levels top at 300 hPa	O ₃ , NO ₂ , CO, PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} from surface stations
MOCHAGE	Météo France	0.2° x 0.2 °	47 levels, top at 5 hPa	O ₃ from surface stations
SILAM	FMI6	0.15° x 0.15°	8 levels, top at 6.7 km	O ₃ , NO ₂ and SO ₂ from surface stations
GEMA-Q	IEP-NRI7	0.1° x 0.1°	28 levels, top at 10 hPa	O ₃ , NO ₂ , CO, SO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5} from surface stations
DEHM	AARHUS UNIVERSITY	18 km, polar stereographic projection	29 layers, top at 100 hPa	O ₃ and NO ₂ from surface stations, PM ₁₀ and PM _{2.5} from global CAMS forecast

MINNI	ENEAS	0.15° x 0.1° regular lat-lon	14 layers, top at 7500 m	NO ₂ , O ₃ , CO, SO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ from surface stations
MONARCH	BSC9	0.15° x 0.1° rotated regular lat-lon	24 layers, top at 50 hPa	NO ₂ , O ₃ , CO, SO ₂ , PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ from surface stations

Source: Collin, 2020 and Marécal et al., 2015

3.2 An Artificial Intelligence based approach for the Arctic

In the past years several models based on Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms have been developed to improve the quality of air forecast pollution at metropolitan and regional spatial scale (e.g. Cordova et al., 2021; Qiu et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024). Such data driven approaches often manage to tackle the limitations of both deterministic and classical statistical models at local dimension (Subramaniam et al., 2022). AI has shown to be a suitable tool to make informed decisions on air pollution mitigation measures to reduce public exposure risk due to its ability to handle complex and non-linear relationships that exist between air quality variables, which allow them to better capture the pollution episodes (Masood & Ahmad, 2021 and references therein). In the European Arctic, the air quality forecast performed by CAMS appears to provide results that agree less with in-situ measurements of PM₁₀ and in Northern Europe with respect to other regions (Schulz et al., 2020) probably due to the limited amount of local air quality monitoring stations (about 20) involved in the assimilation process (CAMS European products support, personal communication, January 16, 2024). To overcome this flaw, Fazzini et al.(2023) developed a forecasting approach for the Arctic based on Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) with the aim of improving PM₁₀ concentrations prediction for geographic locations in the European Arctic (Figure 2). ANNs are inspired by biological neurons and the connections among artificial neurons, called perceptrons, are mathematically expressed as information processed through different functional layers. The data is acquired by the network through a learning process in the input layer; and then the signal is transmitted between neurons in the hidden layers, which perform the computation. The information can be amplified or decreased while transferred among perceptrons, depending on the weights that are continuously updated during the learning phase: the result is then released by the output layer (De Gennaro et al., 2013; Méndez et al., 2023). The basic structure of the multilayer perceptron can be improved in a multitude of ways, depending on the aim of the task, the quality of data and the computational effort. Thus, several variations of the multilayer perceptron can be involved in forecasting tasks dealing with multivariate time series, such as Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) or Echo State Networks (ESNs). Generically speaking, Neural Network modelling involves a four-stage process, consisting of input data selection, design, training and validation: here the details of the framework developed for the Arctic in the study of (Fazzini et al., 2023) is briefly explained for all the stages.

3.2.1 Design

The design phase involves the definition of input and output variables, the choice of an optimal ANN architecture and its main features (Subramaniam et al., 2022). The general architecture proposed in this study consist of an input layer, a memory layer, a dense layer and an output layer (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Left. Geographical localization of the air quality monitoring stations used for model training and testing (red dots) and for ANNs parameters' tuning. The pink dashed region represents the CAMS models area and the green line the AMAP area. Right. ANNs scheme used for the study.

Source: Fazzini et al., 2023

- **Input layer:** Recent studies proved that different ANNs architectures deal well with air quality forecast, however all of those approaches use only time series of pollutants registered by monitoring stations or air quality model predictions as input data (Biancofiore et al., 2017; Cordova et al., 2021; Jia et al., 2019). The conceptual novelty introduced by (Fazzini et al., 2023) consist in combining PM_{10} in situ observation with the 24h CAMS forecast for the selected geographical points as input parameters. In particular, six air quality monitoring stations included in the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program (AMAP) area from the European Environmental Agency (EEA) and Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI) networks were selected since they produced almost complete time series between the time period January 2020-December 2022 (Figure 2, red dots on the map), while two additional stations were selected to provide data for tuning the ANN models' parameters (Figure 2, blue stars on the map). The input vector for the ANNs algorithms was built joining the PM_{10} observation registered by the 6 stations at 00:00 UTC at the current day ($t=0$) and the 24h CAMS forecast ($t=1$) performed by 9 models (CHIMERE, EMEP, EURAD-IM, LOTOS-EUROS, MATCH, MOCHAGE, SILAM, GEMA-Q, DEHM) initialized at $t=0$ (Figure 2). MINNI and MONARCH models were discarded since they do not perform forecast for the Nordic countries. Before feeding the ANNs with the input vector, missing data entries are filled in with linear interpolation and normalized to ensure consistent scaling across the features.
- **Memory layer and dense layer:** the memory layer plays an essential role in the network as it stores the information in the input layer. Five main architectures such as Echo State Networks (ESN), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Gated Recurrent Units (GRU), Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) and Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) were tested in order to explore their performances and select the one that better captures the dynamic of the Arctic PM_{10} time series. The hyperparameters, parameters that control the learning process, were determined using the data of two stations in the Arctic that were not involved in the validation processes (Figure 2, blue stars) to enable the selection of optimal values through an iterative procedure. Those two stations were disregarded during the validation to avoid overfitting. Further details on architectures and hyperparameters tuning can be found in Fazzini et al. (2023).

- **Output layer:** the output layer consists of a single unit layer for the PM₁₀ forecast concentration for each monitoring station at 00:00 UTC of the following day (t=1).

3.2.2 Training and validation

The input data used for the ANNs models training are PM₁₀ measurements from 6 Arctic stations and CAMS forecast for the same geographical points between January 2020 and December 2022 at 00:00 UTC. The time series were split into training set (730 steps) and test set (365 steps). Missing data were filled in with linear interpolation, but the data set was cropped when gaps were larger and it was not possible to apply the linear interpolation. Assuming that observations represent the true PM₁₀ concentration, the forecast results were validated through the calculation of the Mean Square Error (MSE) of the ANNs forecast and the PM₁₀ in situ measurements (Equation 1), then the MSE was compared with the MSE computed for all the CAMS models (Figure 3). The MSE is a unitless value. The ANNs model performances were also compared for the original dataset and for the filtered data set. For the filtered data set, the outliers were selected and removed when they exceeded a defined threshold, set on the lognormal distribution (further details in Fazzini et al., 2023). The validation results showed that all the ANNs architectures exceeds CAMS performances reducing the MSE between 25% to 40%, especially when the outliers were deleted from the datasets (Figure 3). All the ANNs architectures perform similarly in terms of MSE reduction, in particular the LSTM model exhibits the best performances in the scenario where all data are kept, however when outliers are removed both LSTM and ESN show outstanding performances and similar MSE values.

Equation 1: Mean Square Error

$$MSE = \frac{\sum(y_{obs} - y_{pred})^2}{n}$$

Figure 3. MSE for 9 CAMS vs. observations (orange bars, left side of each panel), ANNs models vs. observations (coloured bars, right side of each panel), persistence (red bar, in the middle of each panel) and average (AVE) MSE for all ANNs models (green bar, right side of each panel). Each panel refers to a monitoring station: (a) Muonio, (b) Pyykösjärvi, (c) Oulu, (d) Kópavogur Dalsmári, (e) Grundartangi Gröf, (f) Tromso R.

Source: Fazzini et al., 2023

3.3 Model for AURORAE service

Following the process behind the study by Fazzini et al.(2023), the forecast model employed in the AURORAE service is developed through a comparative analysis of state-of-the-art models for time series forecasting. The aim is to produce a prediction for PM_{10} concentration using historical data from monitoring stations and by taking advantage of air pollution forecasts released by CAMS numerical models. Nonetheless, there are several aspects in which our framework differs from the one in Fazzini et al. Firstly, the number of monitoring stations that provide PM_{10} timeseries is significantly higher (approximately 160 stations vs 6), scattered throughout Northern Europe. Secondly, data resolution is set to hourly concentration collected daily, which accounts for longer time series. Moreover, meteorological variables forecast (boundary layer height, temperature, wind speed components, total precipitation, mean sea level pressure) are added as input feature to improve forecasting accuracy, as previously argued. While these added values can increase the complexity of the task, they also account for a more high-performance model, better suited for the aim of the AURORAE service. The increased amount of data, together with an extension in dimensionality, represent strong limitations to the use of architectures such as RNNs as developed in Fazzini et al., since they might suffer from loss of information due to long-term dependencies. In recent years an increased interest in applications of Natural Language Processing (NLP) models in time series settings has risen; in fact, these architectures show remarkable performances in time series modelling, particularly due to their ability in handling long-range dependencies and sequential

data (Wen et al., 2023). Specifically, by taking inspiration from the Transformer model developed by Vaswani et al. (2017), DL architectures based on such backbone were conceived to approach time series modelling. When dealing with time series forecasting, several of these variations considered networks such as LSTM as baselines in their development and manage to outperform them in multiple domains (Wu et al., 2021; H. Zhou et al., 2021).

3.3.1 Architectures

Due to the promising results brought about such architectures and the intrinsic complexity of the setting, we analysed various Transformer based architectures in the fashion of the study of Fazzini et al. to find the most suitable model for our task.

Transformer based architectures take advantage of three main ingredients :

- Encodings of the spatio-temporal features (geographical coordinates or timestamp) and the sequence position;
- Attention mechanisms, which can arise in different variations;
- Feed-forward networks.

Such ingredients come together in an encoder-decoder architecture, where input data is embedded and encoded in a first phase, and then decoded to produce the output. In more detail, input data is first embedded in a higher dimensional vector space and equipped with the encodings to create an input vector that includes spatio-temporal and sequence related information. The new input vector is then passed on to the attention mechanism, which analyses the input sequence to track down dependencies and underlying patterns; the resulting vector is then passed on to a feed-forward network, ultimately giving the encoded input. The decoder, which is the block in the architecture in charge of producing the output (hence the forecast) takes in part of the input as the initial part of the message to decode, performs attention on such input, and subsequently the outcome is passed on to another attention block which performs on the output of the encoder together with the vector within the decoder. The resulting vector is then passed on to another feed-forward network to produce the decoded output. The blueprint of such architecture (which follows the blocks described by Vaswani et al.) is displayed in Figure 4. Such base model is the one defined as Vanilla Transformer. Informer, Autoformer, FEDformer and Crossformer show variations in the attention mechanisms, but they all keep the same encoder-decoder structure.

Figure 4. Schematic of the Original Vanilla Transformer Architecture

Source: Vaswani et al., 2017

In particular:

- **Informer** applies Probability Sparse Self-Attention, which involves a sparsity measure to identify relevant queries in the attention mechanism (Zhou et al., 2021);
- **Autoformer** acts on the decomposed timeseries with an Autocorrelation mechanism implied as Attention mechanism to find period-based dependencies and aggregates data from sub sequences in period-based decompositions (Wu et al., 2021);
- **FEDformer** inherits the idea of an autoregressive decomposed series generation and aggregation from Autoformer, but implies the representation of the timeseries in the frequency domain rather than in the time domain; the Attention mechanisms are thus superseded by Frequency Enhanced Attention blocks where queries, keys and values are extracted via Fourier Transforms (Zhou et al., 2022);
- **Crossformer** involves the segmentation of input sequence for the initial embedding (Dimension Segment-Wise embedding), a two-stage Cross Attention to capture cross-time and cross-dimension interactions and a Hierarchical Encoder-Decoder structure which accumulates information at different scales (Zhang & Yan, 2023).

3.3.2 Data preparation

Due to the complexity of the task, tuning and training considering all available stations is computationally prohibitive, thus tuning, training and subsequent validation are executed on subsets of the given data. Firstly, from data collected from all stations we consider a selection following the below criteria:

- Data availability for every feature (PM₁₀ concentration, CAMS PM₁₀ forecast and CAMS meteorological variables' forecast need to have compatible availability);
- Number and length of gaps (missing values);
- Heterogeneity in geographic selection (for training we should consider stations from distinct areas of Northern Europe).

Considering the available dates for the collected datasets, the training set considers data from 10th June 2020 to 12th May 2024. From the 164 stations with data availability, we choose 113 the stations which have less than 10% missing values over the full time series, as training/fine-tuning set following the rule of thumb stating that, statistically speaking, we are likely to get a biased result when more than 10% of data is missing (Dong & Peng, 2013; Liu et al., 2020). The remaining stations are used as test set once the model is trained. Amongst the 113 remaining stations, we consider the subset consisting of stations with the longest gap of less than 4 days as the main training set, while the remaining stations will be used for fine-tuning. For model selection and hyperparameter tuning, we consider 5 stations which show the lowest number of missing values (around 0.1-0.2 %). All features are normalized to homogenize the diverse magnitudes and avoid biases in training. For each selected station, we subdivide the associated time series entries in three subsets: 70% of the dataset is considered for training, 10% for validation and 20% for test. We then concatenate the datasets to create unified training, validation and test datasets consisting of data from all of the chosen stations. For training and validation, data samples are shuffled to avoid overfitting. The usage of data is also taken into consideration, as we have several ways of displaying input data for auxiliary variables: both CAMS pollutant concentration models and meteorological variables have availability of 48 hours from the day they are collected, thus in order to predict PM₁₀ concentration at day d we can either use data collected at day $d-1$ (shift=0) or collected at day d (shift=48). For the best performing model, we also include the cases where CAMS meteorological data are not involved as auxiliary variables, in order to evaluate the improvement of the forecast with the use of such indicators.

3.3.3 Model Analysis

Several trials have been carried out to define which model amongst the pinpointed state-of-the-art transformer-based architectures would perform best with given data (Table 2). To evaluate the best performance, every model has been set with standard hyperparameters, with exceptions made for the output length, which was set to 48 (hours), target length for the AURORAE forecast service.

Table 2. Best combination of parameters for each transformer model tested in this study.

Hyperparameter	Transformer	Informer	Autoformer	FEDformer	Crossformer
Input length	96	96	96	96	96
Token length	48	48	48	48	6
Encoder layers	2	4	2	2	3
Decoder layers	1	2	1	1	1
Heads	8	8	8	8	4
Embedding dimension	512	512	512	512	256
Feedforward network dimension	2048	2048	2048	2048	512
Dropout rate	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.2
Learning rate	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}	10^{-4}
Epochs	10	10	10	10	20
Early stopping patience	3	3	3	3	3
Batch size	32	32	32	32	32
Activation	ReLu	GeLu	GeLu	GeLu	GeLu
Loss	MSE	MSE	MSE	MSE	MSE
Optimiser	Adam	Adam	Adam	Adam	Adam
Model specific parameters	-	Factor=3 Distil=True	Moving average=24 Attention factor=3	Attention factor=3 Modes=64	Factor=10 Window size=2

Source: JRC analysis

The evaluation dataset for model analysis consists in the time series from 5 stations characterized by the lowest percentage of missing values (less than 10%): FI_5_15986, FI_5_60955, SE_5_31026, SE_5_62474, FI_5_15584. The experiment for each model was carried out 5 times, and the average MSE and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) (Equation 2) calculated between each model forecast and the PM₁₀ concentration measured by in situ stations are reported in Table 3. The MAE is a unitless value.

Equation 2. Mean Absolute Error.

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_{obs} - y_{pred}|$$

Table 3. MSE ad MAE calculated between model forecast and PM₁₀ in situ observations.

Model	Shift	MSE	MAE
Vanilla Transformer	0	1.213	0.431
Informer	0	1.224	0.433
Autoformer	0	1.735	0.7665
FEDformer	0	1.644	0.754
Crossformer	0	1.141	0.434
Vanilla Transformer	48	1.186	0.428
Informer	48	1.226	0.443
Autoformer	48	1.690	0.750
FEDformer	48	1.605	0.741

Source: JRC analysis

3.3.4 Model Tuning

Our experiments show that among all the teste architectures, the Crossformer is the most suitable model for our task (Table 3) as it minimizes both MSE and MAE. We carried out hyperparameter tuning for this architecture and enhanced the original Crossformer model including the geographical position of the station as further embedding information. Such implementation would allow for a better suited forecast considering the significantly large number of stations, as various pollutants behaviours coming from different areas might introduce noise to the prediction. This geometrical embedding, specifically developed for this study, consists of adding to the original Dimension Segment-Wise (DSW) embedding, a linear embedding of the three geographical coordinates (latitude, longitude, altitude), as embedded in a 3D (standardised) linear space (GDSW). We chose a separate subset of 5 stations (NO_5_28732, NO_5_63001, NO_5_60863, NO_5_43746, NO_5_65126) belonging to the selected 113 stations identified by the criteria to carry out hyperparameter tuning via Grid Search with the following parameter choices showed in Table 4. Our calculations show that defining the Geometric Dimension Segment-Wise (GDSW) embedding outperforms the original Dimension Segment-Wise (DSW) embedding on average over all of the trials. As a result, the best performing models, in terms of MSE and MAE, are reported in Table 5.

We select as the preferred model the Crossformer architecture with the parameters described in the first line of Table 6 as such choices of factor, encoder layers and number of heads have better average score over all trials. Lastly, we verify the benefit from having included the CAMS meteorological parameters forecast as auxiliary variables within the development phase: we check again with the best performing model parameters but excluding the CAMS meteorological variables forecast, this including as input concentrations of PM₁₀ from observations and CAMS predictions. Average scores for trials are summarised in Table 7. The results show that including the meteorological variables bring an average improvement over all the trials.

Table 4. Hyperparameter tuning choices based on 5 selected stations.

Parameter	Choices
Input Length	96, 72
Token Length	6, 12, 24
Data Shift	0, 48
Embedding	DSW, GDSW
Factor	5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10
Encoder Layers	2, 3
Heads	3, 4
Embedding Dimension	128, 256
FeedForward Network Dimension	256, 512
Dropout Rate	0, 0.1, 0.2
Learning Rate	10^{-2} , 10^{-4}

Source: JRC analysis

Table 5. MSE and MAE calculated for the Crossformer model for DSW and GDSW embedding configuration.

Embedding	MSE	MAE
DSW	1.484	0.555
GDSW	1.391	0.535

Source: JRC analysis

Table 6. Parameters such choices of factor, encoder layers and number of heads selected for the Crossformer architecture that show better average score over all trials.

Parameters	Choices test 1	Choices test 2
Input Length	96	96
Token Length	24	24
Data shift	48	48
Embed	GDSW	GDSW
Factor	6	5
Encod Layers	3	2
Heads	4	3
Embed Dimension	256	256
FFN Dimension	512	512
Drop	0.2	0.2
Learn Rate	10^{-4}	10^{-4}
MSE	1.31	1.347
MAE	0.517	0.515

Source: JRC analysis

Table 7. MSE and MAE calculated for trials with Crossformer model including and meteorological variables.

	MSE	MAE
without meteo variables	1.179	0.425
with meteo variables	1.142	0.394

Source: JRC analysis

3.3.5 Model training

The training for the chosen architecture for Crossformer model is run on a dataset consisting of 25 of the 113 selected stations time series. A fine-tuning of the remaining stations with a percentage of missing values below 10% are performed to reduce loss of information. Large gaps (>72h) are cut out to avoid adding bias due to linear interpolation. The training and the fine-tuning are run on one NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000.

4 Implementation of the AURORAE service

The AURORAE service is designed to provide information to non-scientific users such as policymakers, communities' representatives, and citizens regarding near-real time PM₁₀ concentrations registered by monitoring stations in Northern Europe (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Sweden and Norway), and release the PM₁₀ forecast based on Transformer architecture approach.

The AURORAE service is composed by three main modules:

- Data gathering module;
- Forecasting Module;
- Online Platform Module (dashboard).

The Data gathering module collects daily PM₁₀ concentrations from EEA and FMI monitoring stations at 1-hour resolution, CAMS weather meteorological fields forecast, PM₁₀ CAMS forecast for North Europe and treat the data to use them as input for the Forecasting module. The Forecasting module consist in a Crossformer model that provides a 48h PM₁₀ forecast for each monitoring station. The near real time PM₁₀ concentrations and the forecast can be visualized on the Online Platform Module (also called dashboard), an interactive map in which all monitoring stations are represented as dots and the near-real time data and the forecast are accessible as overlapping layers. The dashboard is the information access point for the users to visualized and downloaded the PM₁₀ observation time series and forecast for each station. In addition, a daily air pollution report collecting the current PM₁₀ concentration, the forecast for all monitoring stations and the pollution tendency is released on daily basis and can be downloaded from the AURORAE webpage.

4.1 Data Gathering Module

The Data Gathering Module consists in a series of Python codes that download, gather and process PM₁₀ concentrations data provided by the EEA and FMI for monitoring stations in Norway, Finland, Sweden and Iceland as well as PM₁₀ and meteorological variables forecast released by CAMS. Those data are treated to feed the model and provide a 48h PM₁₀ forecast for the selected monitoring stations on daily basis. Every day at 08:00 UTC an automatic procedure is initiated and the codes that make up the Module are run sequentially. Each code is designed to be run multiple times in one day in case some technical disruptions may terminate the procedure.

4.1.1 EEA and FMI sub-module

The EEA sub-module consist in two Python scripts that download PM₁₀ data concentrations registered by the EEA air quality monitoring stations (<https://eeadmz1-downloads-webapp.azurewebsites.net/>) and that treat the downloaded data sets to create PM₁₀ time series at hourly frequency since June 2020 and updated at daily level. An API request have been created following the EEA guidelines ([https://eeadmz1-downloads-webapp.azurewebsites.net/content/documentation/How To Downloads.pdf](https://eeadmz1-downloads-webapp.azurewebsites.net/content/documentation/How_To_Downloads.pdf)) to download PM₁₀ updated data at daily frequency for all the monitoring stations in Finland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden from the E1 (verified data until 31/12/2022) and E2a (data updated with daily frequency from 01/01/2023) datasets. Each station time series is stored in a parquet file that is converted to a csv file. We merged E1a and E2a time series registered by a monitoring stations only if their data cover the time window form 01/01/2020 until today (2024) with a limited number of missing values (less

than 10%). The time and concentration data are extracted from each csv file and the complete time series for each station is updated on daily basis until 00:00 UTC of the previous day (d=-1). Since the raw time series are set on local time, the final data are converted in UTC time.

The time series of PM₁₀ concentrations measured by FMI monitoring stations are downloaded from the FMI data store website (<https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/download-observations>) for all the Finnish stations at daily frequency until 00:00 UTC of the previous day (d=-1). FMI supplies data through the Web Feature Service (WFS) (<https://www.ogc.org/standard/wfs/>), a generic standard interface for providing access to geospatial objects or objects with some kind of location or covered geospatial area. The access to the FMI data requires the installation of the Python library “fmiopendata”, a specific interface developed for FMI (<https://github.com/pnuu/fmiopendata>), and the creation of an explicit query in order to request the needed dataset. The query for PM₁₀ in situ measurements have been defined following the instructions available in the Open Data WFS service and the stored queries that provide surface observations (<https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/open-data-manual-accessing-data>). The downloaded txt files are then modified by a second code in order to substitute all the values equal to 10000 with “NaN” and to generate a txt file for each station storing the whole time series from January 2020 in UTC time. A separate file is created to store a list of all the FMI air quality stations, their reference codes and the geographical coordinates (<https://en.ilmatieteenlaitos.fi/observation-stations?filterKey=groups&filterQuery=air%20quality%20%28FMI%29>). The datasets produced for all the FMI and EEA stations serve as input files for the forecast model.

4.1.2 CAMS PM₁₀ forecast sub-module

The PM₁₀ concentration forecast released at daily frequency by 9 models of CAMS (CHIMERE, EMEP, EURAD-IM, LOTOS-EUROS, MATCH, MOCHAGE, SILAM, GEMA-Q, DEHM) are downloaded with daily frequency at 08:00 UTC for the current day (t=0) and for the following 48h (t=2) (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/datasets/cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts?tab=download>). We select the model base time at 00:00 UTC and the models’ level at 0 m above the surface. The CAMS models forecast downloaded for the AURORAE service holds the same features summarized in Section 3.1 and Table 2. The CAMS PM₁₀ forecast sub-module is composed by two Python scripts that download the 48 hours forecast covering the European domain at daily frequency and extract the forecast for the geographical position of each station respectively. In particular, the forecast data are stored in NetCDF files and downloaded from the Copernicus Data Store(ACS) catalogue through the CDS Application Programming Interface (API), which requires the registration to the Copernicus website and the installation of the CDS API client, a Python based library (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/how-to-api>). The API request code can be created at the CAMS European air quality forecasts webpage (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/datasets/cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts?tab=download>) after selecting the required fields. The 48 hours forecast is downloaded for each model at daily frequency at 08:00 UTC as a NetCDF file and then the CAMS forecast data are extracted for all EEA and FMI monitoring stations selecting the PM₁₀ values associated to the closest grid point on the models grid. For each monitoring station a txt file is created to store the CAMS models forecast since June 2020 and is updated every day with the new 48 hours forecast (d=2) at hourly resolution. All the produced txt files are used as input for the forecast model.

4.1.3 CAMS weather forecast sub-module

The weather forecast variables represent the third and last input data set for the Crossformer model. The forecast of weather variables is performed by Integrated Forecast System (IFS) of the ECWF (<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/documentation-and-support/changes-ecmwf-model>) and is distributed in association with the CAMS global atmospheric composition forecast (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/datasets/cams-global-atmospheric-composition-forecasts?tab=download>). The IFS employs a four-dimensional variational data assimilation method (4D-VAR) which combines the latest weather observations with a recent forecast to obtain the best possible estimate of the current state of the Earth system. The forecast has a global coverage with model base time at 00:00 UTC and 12:00 UTC, with a horizontal resolution of approximately $0.35^\circ \times 0.35^\circ$ (40 km), an hourly resolution for single level parameters and 3-hours resolution for the multiple levels parameters. The 48 hours IFS forecast with base time at 00:00 UTC is downloaded at 08:00 UTC on daily basis for seven meteorological parameters such as u and v wind components (m/s), Temperature at 2 m above the surface (K), boundary layer height (m), total precipitation (m), mean sea level pressure (Pa) at hourly frequency. All the meteorological variables data are downloaded as NetCDF files using the Copernicus CDS API in the same way it is described for the CAMS PM₁₀ forecast sub-module. The time series of the IFS meteorological parameters are extracted for all EEA and FMI monitoring stations, selecting each variable values on the grid points closer to each stations geographical position. For every monitoring station and meteorological variable, a txt file is created to store the IFS forecast since June 2020 and is updated every day with the new 48 hours forecast (d=2) at hourly resolution. All the produced txt files are used as input for the forecast model.

4.2 Forecasting Module

The forecasting module consists of two mostly independent submodules: the main module performs the 48h forecast for PM₁₀ concentration, while an independent submodule manages the update of weights for the model once enough new data has been collected to feed the architecture.

4.2.1 Forecasting sub-module

The main module is run every day to allow for new forecasts of particulate for each of the available stations. In fact, it operates sequentially with the following tasks:

- Find all available stations and checks that each of the variables has been downloaded correctly, thus creates a list of updated stations;
- Collects data from each of the variable's dataset to create input vector for the model for each station;
- Performs prediction for each feasible station;
- Releases a quality assessment of the prediction based on data availability for each station.

In particular, the forecasting module will rely on a pre-trained model which was trained by using historical data from the available stations. As described in the previous section, the chosen model is a variation of the original Crossformer architecture from Zhang & Yan (2023).

4.2.2 Update sub-module

The pre-trained model only uses historical data, without taking into account newly downloaded data. As the model might benefit from being fed newer data, an update module has been considered to fine tune the pre-trained model with data which has not yet been seen by the model. To do so, we set a timeframe of 2160 hours (approx. 3 months) where new data is collected before feeding it to the network. The update submodule is then structured as follows:

- A daily check is run to verify whether the timeframe period has been reached;
- If enough time has passed since the latest update, the update module is run; otherwise, no additional task is run;
- When the update module is run, the pre-trained model is loaded;
- Once the pre-trained model is loaded, new batches of data collected during the timeframe are fed to the model;
- The updated model is then tested and if it outperforms the previously pre-trained model, the updated model is used as the standard model for forecast from the day after the tuning.

The performance is measured through MSE and MAE averaged over all the available stations and over the timeframe. All model weights updated during fine tuning phase, also called checkpoints, will be stored.

4.2.3 Migration issues

Due to the server migration for data coming from EEA stations, some information about stations and data availability have changed since the preliminary training for the main model was completed. A quality assessment of the migrated data, as well as a comparison with the available stations, is being carried out to deliver a pre-trained model which is best adapted to the dynamic input data.

4.3 Online Platform Module

The AURORAE web application is built within a JupyterLab environment, a widely used platform for data science. It is developed using Jupyter Notebooks, which integrate code, text, and multimedia in a single document. To enhance the user experience, the open source Voilà tool (<https://github.com/voila-dashboards/voila>) is used to render these notebooks as interactive web applications, displaying outputs without exposing the underlying code. This approach enables the creation of sophisticated, data-driven applications where users can interact with data through intuitive graphical interfaces. The AURORAE dashboard is implemented in Python programming language, leveraging various libraries that facilitate page construction, information presentation, and user interaction through graphical widgets. One of these libraries is VOIS, an open-source project developed by the JRC and hosted in the code.europa.eu repository (<https://code.europa.eu/jrc-bdap/vois>). VOIS simplifies the process of creating appealing visualizations within the Voilà environment, making it easier for developers to build engaging, interactive applications.

The overall platform is hosted on Microsoft Azure web service instance. Currently, the employment of a commercial cloud solution to host the dashboard answers to the business needs to have an ac-

cessible website without any restrictions. Instead, JRC, at this moment, does not fully support the deployment of dashboard without an EU login access. This approach responded to the needs of creating a flexible website which runs with minimum costs. The Azure cloud's cost management service helps the users keep the costs under control with a detailed cost breakdown and analysis tools. The VMs used to host the dashboard have a cost of around 3.72€ per day. The app service plan selected for this amount offers 2 cores and 16 Giga Byte (GB) of RAM (Random Access Memory), but the "scale-up scale-out" Azure capability can be configured to allocate more computational resources to the VM serving the dashboard or allocate more VM, according to the incoming request to access the dashboard, in a flexibly way.

4.4 Data flow

The main objective of the AURORAE service is to gather and process data in diverse format (txt, parquet, NetCDF, etc) from different sources (EEA, FMI, CAMS) to feed the Crossformer model to forecast the PM₁₀ concentrations which are updated at daily frequency and available to final user. The data are downloaded from external APIs at daily frequency and the forecast is performed on the JRC Big Data Analytics Platform (BDAP), a versatile multi-petabyte scale platform based on storage co-located with a high-throughput computing capacity (Soille et al., 2018). After the source data has been ingested and the forecast model has generated and computed the new forecast data, all information is uploaded to a GitHub repository. The dashboard uses the GitHub repository as data source to display on-the-fly the most recent data. The GitHub repository link will be available soon on the AURORAE website.

Figure 5. Schematic of the data flow for the AURORAE service.

Source: JRC analysis

4.5 Technical requirements

The AURORAE service and its modules are developed in Python programming language (version 3.10.14) (<https://www.python.org/downloads/release/python-3100/>) and are hosted in the JEODPP platform. The Data Gathering Module has been built and tested via Spyder IDE (<https://www.spyder-ide.org/>) and PyCharm Integrated Development Environment (IDE) (<https://www.jetbrains.com/pycharm/>), while the the Forecasting and the Online Platform Modules developing has been carried out via Jupyter (<https://jupyter.org/>) notebooks . The Crossformer

forecast model implemented in the dashboard employs the following Python packages: Numpy 1.26.4(<https://numpy.org/>), Pandas 2.2.1 (<https://pandas.pydata.org/>), PyTorch 2.3.0 (<https://pytorch.org/>), TensorFlow™ (<https://www.tensorflow.org/>).

The online dashboard is developed in Python 3.10. The main libraries used are: the VOIS library (<https://code.europa.eu/jrc-bdap/vois>) for the creation of the GUI components (such as buttons, labels, etc..), Plotly (<https://github.com/plotly/plotly.py>) to display the data, ipyleaflet (<https://github.com/jupyter-widgets/ipyleaflet>) to display geo-data on an interactive map and voila to deploy the resulting Jupyter notebook into a web application. The web application is hosted within a web service provided by Microsoft Azure. The data are hosted on GitHub to make them accessible to everyone.

5 The AURORAE Service Web Dashboard

The AURORAE service web dashboard is developed in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Arctic PASSION project, which aims at co-creating and implementing a coherent, integrated Arctic observing system: the ‘Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems - pan-AOSS’, overcoming the flaws in the present observing systems by refining its operability, improving, and extending pan-Arctic scientific and community-based monitoring and the integration with Indigenous and Local knowledge, by streamlining the access and interoperability of Arctic Data systems and services (<https://arcticpassion.eu/intro>). Since the current observational systems for the Arctic environment are fragmented, incoherent, and not tuned to the users’ needs, one of the project goals consists in creating free services for non-specialists living and/or working in the Arctic. Those services envision to add value to the environmental data, address urgent users’ needs and empower the civil society, policymakers and private sector to observe, understand and predict future changes in the Arctic. Eight services are developed within Arctic PASSION, spanning various topics from permafrost thawing to fire risk management and lake ice forecast. All the services can be accessed from the Arctic Window page at the project website (<https://arcticpassion.eu/arcticwindow/services>).

The AURORAE dashboard providing the ‘Local air pollution forecast service’ consists of a web interface to monitor the air quality of the North European countries on daily basis and to provide 48 hours forecast of PM₁₀ concentrations. At the moment there is no specific air quality forecast service designed for Northern communities. The forecast produced by CAMS in the European Arctic appears to provide results that agree less with in-situ measurements of PM₁₀ and the CAMS Atmosphere Data Store supplies data in GRIB or NetCDF formats, accessible only by experts. The AURORAE service, on the other hand, releases a PM₁₀ forecast tailored for the European Arctic and designed to be user-friendly; the webpage can be navigated by a non-scientific public such as citizens and policymakers. In addition, the air pollution forecast information is conveyed with a plain design and a bulletin gathering the near-real time PM₁₀ concentrations and the forecast for all the stations is released on a daily basis. The service aims at empowering Nordic and Arctic communities on relevant topics such air quality and its effects on public health, and to promptly take action in case of episodes of high level of air pollution.

5.1 Access to the dashboard

The AURORAE service dashboard is accessible without registration and without a EU Login Account at the following link: <https://aurorae.azurewebsites.net>. The website is expected to be fully operational in 2025. We aim at distributing a forecast service that is easily accessible by both expert and non-expert users, with an open access website and documentation following the European Commission Guidelines for Horizon 2020 projects.

5.2 Structure of the dashboard

The landing page of the AURORAE dashboard consists in a web page divided in 3 main sections: a navigation panel, an interactive map and a time series window (Figure 6). The navigation panel is located on the left side of the webpage, the user can choose what data to visualize on the interactive maps selecting one of the 3 available buttons: “Measured”, “Forecast 1-day” and “Forecast 2-day”. Once the user clicks on the chosen button, the selected air pollution data are displayed on the main panel of the webpage consisting in the interactive map. The date to which the data refers to is displayed on the top of the page. The map is a geographic layer where all the air pollution monitoring

stations are drawn as coloured circles at their specific geographical location. The map allows to zoom in and out the view, and to facilitate the interpretation of the air quality status; each circle is coloured in green, orange or red depending on the PM₁₀ concentration level at site according to the EEA health-based classification (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/explore-interactive-maps/up-to-date-air-quality-data>), while grey colour indicates the absence of data. The specific PM₁₀ concentration (24-hours average) at each station can be obtained by clicking on the chosen circle, the station information such as coordinates, station code and network are displayed on the left side of the map. Moreover, if the users want to search for a specific station, the lens icon on the navigation panel allows to look for a specific monitoring station by name or code. After selecting a station, either using the lens or clicking on the station circle on the map, the hourly resolution PM₁₀ concentration trend over time at that specific location is automatically displayed in the double window at the bottom of the page. The left panel shows the full time series recorded by the station, while the right panel displays the past week PM₁₀ concentrations as a blue curve and the 48h and the forecast for the following 2 days at hourly resolution is shown as a red curve.

Figure 6. The landing page of the AURORAE Service.

Source : AURORAE website (<https://aurorae.azurewebsites.net/>)

5.3 Accessing and downloading data

The PM₁₀ forecasted concentrations at monitoring stations locations provided by the AURORAE service is available also in format of downloadable txt files. For each station the PM₁₀ concentrations 48h forecast at hourly resolution can be obtained clicking on the icon when selecting a monitoring station from the map or using the searching lens. Each file is named after the EEA or FMI unique station code. In addition, a “Daily air quality bulletin” is released every day from the service and can be obtained clicking on the button “Download daily bulletin” at the top left of the page. The bulletin is a txt file composed by 11 columns where the first 7 columns hold the information regarding the monitoring stations, such as station code, country, network name and coordinates while the last the last 4 columns report the mean PM₁₀ concentration registered by the station the previous day d-1

(until 00:00 UTC), the mean of the forecasted PM₁₀ concentration for the following 24 hours (d) and for the following 48 hours (d+1). The last column is planned to evaluate the quality of the forecast. The validation method is not finalized yet and this report will be updated on that matter in next version. A guide that helps the users to navigate the website and download will be available clicking on the guide icon on the upper right side of the webpage.

Figure 7: Example of the AURORAE daily air pollution bulletin file

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
Station Co	Station Name	Country	Network	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Date	PM10 mean cur	PM10 24h mean forecast	PM10 48h mean forecast	Forecast Quality
FI_5_1543	Sammalkunturi	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	background	67.96713	24.12215	6/5/2024	2.85076825	4.6599854	4.8018925	3
FI_5_1547	Rautionkylä	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	industrial	61.23807	28.87365	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan
FI_5_1548	Kallio 2	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	background	60.18759	24.9506	6/5/2024	10.25774429	10.223159	8.796183	3
FI_5_1548	Pirkkala	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	industrial	61.53164	22.54366	6/5/2024	8.02961342	14.326657	12.111254	3
FI_5_1550	Kalvola	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	industrial	61.31465	22.13169	6/5/2024	8.529812683	12.235178	12.171489	3
FI_5_1550	Mannerheimintie	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	60.16964	24.93934	6/5/2024	22.6616525	23.008292	17.856284	3
FI_5_1551	Uusniemi	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	60.96704	25.65489	6/5/2024	13.78194892	14.835321	11.90934	3
FI_5_1553	Lauritsala	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	61.07194	28.26409	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan
FI_5_1553	Pyyköjärvi	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	background	65.04938	25.4579	6/5/2024	11.67634711	10.125245	11.929160	3
FI_5_1557	Virolahti 2	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	background	60.52002	27.6754	nan	nan	nan	nan	nan
FI_5_1558	Maaherankatu	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	62.89333	27.48688	6/5/2024	9.108432875	28.0289	23.951477	3
FI_5_1560	Oulun keskusta 2	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	65.00997	25.47332	6/5/2024	18.488398	14.679123	16.24539	3
FI_5_1561	Lappeenranta keskus	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	61.05576	28.18431	6/5/2024	14.81157933	17.148323	16.67967	3
FI_5_1563	Epilä 2	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	61.50004	31.67883	6/5/2024	6.418098417	9.348592	10.822030	3
FI_5_1564	Tasavallankatu	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	62.88138	27.46192	6/5/2024	63.30313813	32.799015	29.211046	3
FI_5_1564	Keskusta Pirkkälänselkä	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	65.88764	23.13318	6/5/2024	15.70774463	10.086346	13.218922	3
FI_5_1569	Raahen keskusta 2	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	64.68037	24.48362	6/5/2024	9.401067625	10.357938	14.368331	3
FI_5_1575	Vaasa virastom	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	background	65.09051	21.61267	6/5/2024	91.57918504	1.3881571	2.55974	3
FI_5_1577	Luzuki	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	background	60.51439	24.88486	6/5/2024	7.653175042	7.801091	8.8652145	3
FI_5_1578	Manikkala	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	61.18892	28.77012	6/5/2024	10.47098654	21.413856	20.30957	3
FI_5_1580	Lappeenranta 4	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	60.22024	24.81133	6/5/2024	13.82471313	14.095852	11.96587	3
FI_5_1580	Tikkurila 3	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	60.28995	25.89653	6/5/2024	16.96077338	12.696329	10.437856	3
FI_5_1585	Vartiokylä Huijoc	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	background	60.23293	25.10344	6/5/2024	11.04689868	11.595252	9.756511	3
FI_5_1587	Pirkankatu	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	61.49673	23.73569	6/5/2024	10.72019367	14.168861	13.418496	3
FI_5_1590	Joutsenon keskusta	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	61.11709	28.49849	6/5/2024	11.97541066	22.001226	15.22887	3
FI_5_1593	Sottensvikaalagen	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	63.67912	22.71817	6/5/2024	24.12604654	8.445493	10.899192	3
FI_5_1598	Vaasan keskusta	FI	European Environmental Agency (EEA)	traffic	67.06515	21.61832	6/5/2024	9.478996417	9.033539	8.922566	3

Source: JRC analysis

6 Results

In section 2.1 “Model for AURORAE service”, we described the architecture and the related studies to define a suitable as well as effective model to deal with the available data. Such studies led to the best performing Crossformer model with hyperparameters defined by the values in Table 8.

Table 8. Summary of the hypapramters of the Crossformer model employed in the AURORAE service.

Parameter	Choices
Input Length	96
Token Length	24
Data Shift	48
Embedding	GDSW
Factor	6
Encoder Layers	3
Heads	4
Embedding Dimension	256
FeedForward Network Dimension	512
Dropout Rate	0.2
Learning Rate	10^{-4}

Source: JRC analysis

The preferred architecture trained on 5 stations from the selection (FI_5_15986, FI_5_60955, SE_5_31026, SE_5_62474, FI_5_15584) chosen by criteria presented in section 2.1.2 “Data Preparation” (data availability, missing values count, geographical heterogeneity) was evaluated on the test set described by the 20% of the available data (approximately a yearlong collection from each station). The metrics for this evaluation are described in Table 9.

Table 9. MSE and MAE calculated for the Crossformer model applied in the AURORAE service.

	MSE	MAE
Improved Crossformer	1.099	0.412

Source: JRC analysis

We can compare the performance of our improved Crossformer model with the one from deterministic models provided by CAMS. For each of the selected CAMS models, the metrics evaluated on the same test set give the estimates summarized in Table 10.

Table 10. MSE and MAE calculated comparing our improved Crossformer model forecast with the one from deterministic models provided by CAMS.

CAMS model	MSE	MAE
CHIMERE	2.378	0.866
DEHM	1.793	0.740
EMEP	2.080	0.792
EURADIM	2.520	0.925
GEMA-Q	1.618	0.672
LOTOS	2.166	0.826
MATCH	2.817	1.132
MOCAGE	2.458	0.934
SILAM	1.917	0.768

Source: JRC analysis

The aforementioned evaluations result in a prediction improvement of approximately 32% on the MSE and of approximately 39% on the MAE comparing the improved Crossformer with the best performing CAMS model (GEMA-Q) (Figure 8). Ultimately, we developed a specified predictive model with Transformer based architecture which manages to efficiently assimilate heterogeneous data as well as produce a prediction which outperforms the state-of-the-art deterministic models.

Figure 8. Comparison of MSE calculated between the observations and the CAMS and the Crossformer models. The Crossformer outperforms all the CAMS models reducing the error by 32%.

Source: JRC analysis

7 Connection with INFRA Service

In the framework of the ArcticPASSION project, several Arctic services have been developed including the Integrated Fire Risk Management (INFRA) Service (<https://arcticpassion.eu/wp4/ps4/>). INFRA is a web mapping service for wildfires to make the access to relevant information and products easier from diverse sources. Focusing on a local scale, the service provides the possibility to generate and distribute messages on wildfires that are tailored to non-scientific end-users like municipalities, as well as Indigenous Peoples and local communities. The service currently covers test areas of about 1500x 1500 km located in Sacha-Yakutia, Fennoscandia and Alaska. In the Arctic, wildfires represent a relevant source of PM₁₀ emissions especially North America (Canada and Alaska) and Siberia; for this reason the developers of both services set up a connection between INFRA and AURORAE services with the aim of combining the information relative to wildfires with the data related to air pollution. Specifically, the AUROARE service is equipped with a Wildfire module that transfers the following datasets to the INFRA service on daily basis via an HTTPS/FTPS service:

- CAMS forecast of PM₁₀ fraction emitted by wildfires.
- Flux of total PM₁₀ emitted by wildfires.

The CAMS forecast of PM₁₀ fraction emitted by wildfires data are released at daily frequency by 9 models of CAMS, as for the PM₁₀ CAMS forecast, and are downloaded with daily frequency at 08:00 UTC for the current day (t=0) and for the following 48h (t=2) (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/cams-europe-air-quality-forecasts?tab=form>) by the AURORAE automatic procedure. We select the model base time at 00:00 UTC and the models' level at 0 m above the surface. To download, treat the netCDF files and produce the text (.txt) files for each EEA and FMI in situ monitoring stations we developed a submodule (two Python scripts) like the one created for the CAMS PM₁₀ forecast and described in section 4.1.2.

The wildfire flux of total PM (kg m⁻² s⁻¹) is released at daily frequency at 07:00 UTC by the CAMS global biomass burning emissions based on fire radiative power (GFAS) (<https://ads.atmosphere.copernicus.eu/datasets/cams-global-fire-emissions-gfas?tab=download>) that assimilates fire radiative power (FRP) observations from satellite-based sensors to produce daily estimates of biomass burning emissions. CAMS GFAS data covers the period from 2003 to present, and includes: FRP, dry matter burnt and biomass burning emissions (<https://confluence.ecmwf.int/display/CKB/CAMS+global+biomass+burning+emissions+based+on+fire+radiative+power+%28GFAS%29%3A+data+documentation>).

The features of the current version of CAMS GFAS (GFAS v1.2) are:

- Injection height daily data (Mean altitude of maximum injection and Altitude of plume top) as provided by the Plume Rise Model and IS4FIRES Flux of total PM₁₀ emitted by wildfires.
- Pixel based quality control for the MODIS instruments on Aqua and Terra.
- Statistical regression of the output when assimilating only Aqua or Terra observations so as to preserve consistency with data obtained assimilating Aqua and Terra observations.

The wildfire flux of total PM is downloaded everyday as a single netCDF file that covers the whole globe, the data are extracted selecting the variable 'tpmfire'. The file is cropped on the areas of

Yakutia and Canada and Alaska, and two files are saved as a raster image (.tiff extension). Those images are displayed on the INFRA webpage.

8 Stakeholders consultations and recommendations

The AUROARE service is a website designed for Northern European and Arctic municipalities and citizens to provide an improved and accessible air quality forecast. The aim of the service is to empower people living and working in these areas on topics such as air pollution and its effects on human health. In addition, the service is also developed to help communities to monitor air pollution in their area, to plan mitigation actions and to foresee protection actions in case of high pollution events.

Considering that the service has been tailored for non-professional users, it is necessary for the authors of this report to obtain feedbacks from potential users to improve the website and to provide a service designed for their specific needs.

The AURORAE service has been presented at the following conferences:

- ArcticPASSION General Assembly 2023, 22-26 May 2023, Laveno (Italy)
- Arctic Frontiers 2024, 29 January-1 February 2024, Tromsø (Norway)
- Arctic Science Summit Week 2024, 21-29 March 2024, Edinburgh (UK) – online presentation
- ArcticPASSION General Assembly 2024, 11-13 June, Inari (Finland)
- EU Polar Science Week, 3-6 September, Copenhagen (Denmark)
- APECS and ArcticPASSION Webinar, 29 October 2024 – online presentation

During the discussion with the public we gathered the following recommendations that are planned to be implemented:

- Add on the website information on the recommended actions that need to be taken by citizens in order to protect themselves by air pollution depending on the PM₁₀ concentrations;
- Make the website more interactive enabling users to add information regarding sources of atmospheric pollution in their area, report an extreme event of pollution in their municipality or provide any information considered to be relevant;
- Add in-situ stations located in Denmark in the website and provide the forecast at those geographical positions.

The AURORAE website will be presented at future conferences and distributed through stakeholders' networks such as Arctic Majors' Forum and WWF Arctic. All the additional feedbacks will be considered and eventually implemented.

9 Conclusions

The Arctic, once considered a pristine environment, has been experiencing atmospheric pollution since the 1950s, with the phenomenon of Arctic Haze. The recent increase in global warming has created opportunities for economic activities such as shipping and oil and gas extraction, leading to a rise in local sources of atmospheric pollution (Law et al., 2017). This pollution has significant implications for public health, making it essential to provide accurate and reliable short-term forecasts to support governments and stakeholders in developing policies to limit population exposure. The Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) provides forecasts of PM₁₀ concentrations over Europe, including the Arctic, however these predictions are subject to uncertainties.

To address these discrepancies and provide an accessible tool to Arctic citizens and communities we developed an Arctic Service, within the Horizon 2020 project ArcticPASSION, called AURORAE (Air Quality foRecast foR Arctic communitiEs). The AURORAE service is an accessible, interactive and user-friendly platform that features 48 hours PM₁₀ forecasts for around 100 monitoring stations and near-real-time concentration for Northern European countries. To provide an accurate PM₁₀ forecast an ad-hoc Deep Learning model has been implemented. We tested several model architectures among the category of Transformers and we selected the Crossformer model, which improves the MSE and MAE approximately by 32% and 39% respectively when compared with the best performing CAMS model (GEMAQ). This innovative approach combines in-situ measurements from about 100 monitoring stations, 48 hours CAMS PM₁₀ forecasts, and a 48 hours forecast of 6 meteorological variables produced by the ECMWF for countries in the European Arctic.

The AURORAE service shows several key benefits, including:

- Improved accuracy: The service provides more accurate PM₁₀ forecasts than CAMS, particularly in the Arctic region;
- Enhanced user experience: The service offers a user-friendly interface that allows non-experts to access and understand air quality forecasts;
- Increased accessibility: The service provides near-real-time PM₁₀ concentrations and forecasts for over 100 monitoring stations in Northern Europe and the Arctic.
- Support for decision-making: The service provides a daily air quality bulletin that summarizes the current air quality situation and forecast for all monitoring stations, enabling informed decision-making.

The development of the AURORAE service has demonstrated the potential of Deep Learning models to improve air quality forecasting, particularly in regions with limited data coverage. The service has also highlighted the importance of stakeholder engagement and collaboration in the development of environmental services. Future developments for AURORAE include the integration with the INFRA (Integrated Fire Risk Management) service, in order to provide information on air pollution produced by Arctic wildfires, and enhance the user experience and accessibility of the website following the users' feedbacks and recommendations.

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List of abbreviations and definitions

Abbreviations	Definitions
4D-VAR	Four-Dimensional Variational Data Assimilation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMAP	Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Program
API	Application Programming Interface
AURORAE	Air qUality foRecast fOR Arctic communitiEs
CAMS	Copernicus Atmopsheric Monitoring Service
CDS	Copernic Data Store
CTMs	Chemical Transport Models
DL	Deep Learning
DL	Deep Learning
DSW	Dimension Segment-Wise
ECMWF	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
EEA	European Environmental Agency
EMEP	European Monitoring and Evaluation Programme
ESN	Echo State Networks
EU	European Union
FMI	Finnish Meteorological Institute
GB	Giga Byte
GDSW	Geometric Dimension Segment-Wise
GFAS	Global Biomass Burning Emissions Based on Fire Radiative Power

Abbreviations	Definitions
GRU	Gated Recurrent Units
IDE	Integrated Development Environment
IFS	Integrated Forecast System
INFRA	Integrated Fire Risk Management
JRC	Joint Research Centre
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MLP	Multilayer Perceptron
MSE	Mean Square Error
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NN	Neural Network
PM	Particulate Matter
PM ₁₀	Particulate Matter with diameter smaller than 10 µm
PS	Pilot Service
RAM	Random Access Memory
RNN	Recurrent Neural Networks
UTC	Coordinated Universal Time

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